

Intellectual
Property
Office

Certificate of Registration for a UK Design

Design number: 6501006

Grant date: 04 February 2026

Registration date: 23 January 2026

This is to certify that,

in pursuance of and subject to the provision of Registered Designs Act 1949, the design of which a representation or specimen is attached, had been registered as of the date of registration shown above in the name of

Dr. Kanade Ashok Tukaram, Devarshi Dutta, Dr. Rajkumar Krishna Pillai, Minal

Ajay Pardey, Dr. Ruma Bhadauria, Dr. Arockiasamy Savitha Mary, Dr.

Chandrashekhar Shankarrao Patil, Dr. Prakash Dubey, Dr. Naga Durga

Malleswararao Koratla, Mrs. Undavalli Krupa, Chigurupati Sudharani, Kolli

Venkata Siva Nagendra Jawahar Babu

in respect of the application of such design to:

AI BASED DATA PRIVACY CHECKING DEVICE

International Design Classification:

Version: 15-2025

Class: 10 CLOCKS AND WATCHES AND OTHER MEASURING
INSTRUMENTS, CHECKING AND SIGNALLING INSTRUMENTS

Subclass: 05 INSTRUMENTS, APPARATUS AND DEVICES FOR CHECKING,
SECURITY OR TESTING

Adam Williams

Comptroller-General of Patents, Designs and Trade Marks
Intellectual Property Office

The attention of the Proprietor(s) is drawn to the important notes overleaf.

Representation of Designs

Intellectual Property Office is an operating name of the Patent Office

www.gov.uk/ipo